

PARASURGICAL MANAGEMENT BY VIDDHAKARMA IN MADAROSIS (PAKSHMASHATA) -A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Madarosis can be correlated with *Pakshmachata* which is having common clinical features, hair loss i.e., eyebrow hypotrichosis. According to Acharya Vagbhata, falling out of hair from its surface is due to vitiation of *Vata Dosh* mainly. Acharya Sushruta says *Khalitya* is primarily a *Pitta* predominant *Tridoshajanya Vyadhi* (all three *Doshas* vitiated disease). Genetics and hormonal level imbalance in the body may leads to eye brow hair loss. In Vagbhata Samhita *Uttara tantra*,^[1] *Romkoop Vikuttana*, *Jalaukavcharana*, *Vamana*, *Nasya*, *Lepam* are given for the treatment of *Pakshmachata*. **Materials and method:** It is single case study of 20 years old male patient with complaint of hair loss over left eyebrow since 4 months. This case of Madarosis (*Pakshmachata*) was successfully treated with 12 sittings (2 sittings per week) of *Viddhakarma* for one and half month

duration. **Result:** The patch was immensely filled with lustrous black hairs with density at the end of the followup period. **Conclusion:** *Viddhakarma* showed promising results in eyebrow hair loss. It is effective, economical, and less invasive procedure, can be perform in patients suffering from Madarosis.

KEY WORDS: Madarosis, *Pakshmachata*, *Viddhakarma*.

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of eyebrow hair loss, while often considered a benign sign, can actually serve as a crucial indicator of underlying health conditions. Madarosis, resulting in thinning or patchy eyebrows.^[2] Similarly, autoimmune disorders like alopecia areata and dermatological conditions such as eczema, psoriasis, and lichen planus can also contribute to eyebrow hair loss.^[3] In Ayurveda, eyebrow hair fall is attributed to imbalances in the *Vata* and *Pitta doshas*, resulting in conditions like *Pakshmathata* and *Khalitya*. These ancient texts describe how vitiated *Pitta* and *Vata* disrupt the hair follicles, leading to hair loss and hindering regrowth. In Ayurveda, practices like *Rom koop vikuttana* (using a sterile needle to stimulate blood flow in hair follicles), *Jalaukavcharana* (leech therapy), *vamana*, *nasya*, and *lepam* are recommended for conditions like *Pakshmathata*.^[4] *Abhyangam*, by combining traditional wisdom with contemporary interventions madarosis management can be done effectively.^[5]

CASE STUDY

A 20-year male patient with occupation as a student was reported to Shalakya OPD.

History of present illness: Patient was asymptomatic before 4 months. Then He gradually started to have asymptomatic hair loss over the left eyebrow.

Examination: Bald patch over his 2/3 of left eyebrow along with occasional itching. Right eyebrow was normal.

History of past illness: There was no specific history of similar complaints in his family. No history of drug intake and no history suggestive of any systemic disease.

Personal history

Aahara: *Pitta and Vaata Vardark* (Excess Junk Food)

Vyasana: None

Vyayama: None

Nidra: *Asamyaka, Ratrijagaran, Divaswaap.*

Koshtha: *Kroora, Malavshambha* 1Time/Day ,Hard Stoola.

Mootra Pravritti: *Samyaka*

Agni: *Vishama.*

Jaran Shakti: *Madyama*

Abhyavaran Shakti: *Madhyama*

Pramaan: Height 5.5 Feet, Weight: 57 kg

Satmya: Pravara Satva: Madhyama PrakritiVaata Pittaj.

DIAGNOSIS

After thorough clinical examination patient was diagnosed as Madarosis. (Fig-1). Clinical features were resembling with *Pakshamakshaata*.

Treatment Plan

Para surgical management with *Viddhakarma* was planned to perform twice in a week. Along with oral medication.

Viddhakarma Procedure

Purva karma: Supine position given to patient. Both the eyes were covered with eye bandage.

Pradhana Karma: Affected site of eyebrow was cleaned with betadine solution. Multiple pricks were taken directly on bald patch of the site. Depth of prick was kept 1/8 *vrihi pramaan* approximately 2mm by using 26 no. ½ inch (13 mm) needle. After *viddhakarma* blood oozing occurred which was allowed to ooze and then after it is wiped with sterile piece of guaze. Procedure was uneventful.

Paschaat karma: After procedure site was cleaned with betadine solution.

Table 1: Internal Medicine.

Sr.no.	Name of medicine	Dose	Duration
1.	Polyherbal Capsule	2 cap. Two times a day after food with lukewarm water.	First 3 weeks
2.	<i>Amalaki rasayana</i>	1 tab Two times a day after food with lukewarm water.	Last 3 Weeks

RESULT

At the beginning of the treatment patient was having bald patch over his left eyebrow. After 4 sittings of *viddhakarma* new hair growth was noticed at site. Significant dense hair growth was observed after completion of 10 sittings of *viddhakarma*. Weekly assessment was done to observe hair growth. After 6 weeks bald patch was completely covered with hairs. (Fig-2). *Viddhakarma* procedure and internal medicines were stopped. After completion of

management patient was asked to give monthly follow-up for next three months. No recurrence was occurred.

Images

DISCUSSION

In present case diagnosis of *pakshashaat* was made based on clinical presentation. Acharya Sushruta has mentioned vitiated *Pitta* and *Vata* disrupt the hair follicles, leading to hair loss and hindering regrowth.^[7] Acharyas have mentioned *Rom koop vikuttana* management for this condition.^[8] As per accordance with this *Viddhakarma* which is a modified type of *raktamokshana* was performed in this case using a sterile needle.^[9]

Probable mode of action: *Viddhakarma* stimulates blood flow and increases micro blood circulation towards hair follicles. Increased blood circulation helps to remove accumulated toxins, inflammatory substances and enhances the delivery of nutrients to hair roots which results in new hair growth.

CONCLUSION

Proper diagnosis and management are essential not only for restoring eyebrow growth but also for addressing underlying health concerns. *Viddhakarma* along with internal medicines showed promising results in eyebrow hair loss (madarosis). *Viddhakarma* is effective, economical, and less invasive procedure. Hence, if done on large sample size, this management can become a successful treatment protocol for the management of eyebrow hair loss (madarosis).

Patient consent Statement

The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate patient consent form. In the form, patient has given his consent images and other clinical information to be reported in the

journal. The patient understand that his name and initials will not be published and due efforts will be made to conceal their identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Vagbhatta, K.R.Shrikanthamurthy, Astanga hridayam, Uttarasthana chapter 9: Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi.
2. Price VH. Treatment of hair loss. N Engl J Med., 1999; 23(341): 964–73. [PubMed] [Google Scholar].
3. Alkhalifah A. Topical and intralesional therapies for alopecia areata. Dermatol Ther., 2011; 24: 355–63. [PubMed] [Google Scholar].
4. Susuruta chikitsa sthana 1/101: Chaukhambha sanskruta sansthana Varanasi.
5. Sulabha K. Kulkarni Nanotechnology, principle & practise, capital publishing company, 1st edition, 2007; preface ix.
6. Shubham Jain and et all, IOSR-JPBS, ISSN: 2278-3008, vol-11: 58-63.
7. Vagbhatta KR Shrikanthamurthy, Astanga hridayam, Uttarasthana chapter 9: Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi.
8. Vagbhatta KR. Shrikanthamurthy, Astanga hridayam, Uttarasthana chapter 8/8: Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi.
9. Singhal GD et al. Sushruta Samhita, Second edition, Bangalore, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishtan, Part.1 Nidana Sthana., Ch.13/32-33: 2014; 316.